

Ethical mathematics awareness in students' big data decision making

Michelle Stephan, University of North Carolina at Charlotte, mstepha1@uncc.edu

Jordan Register, University of North Carolina at Charlotte

Luke Reinke, University of North Carolina at Charlotte

David Pugalee, University of North Carolina at Charlotte

Lenora Crabtree, University of North Carolina at Charlotte

Christine Robinson, University of North Carolina at Charlotte

Premkumar Pugalenti, Palisades Episcopal Schools

In this paper, we investigate adolescent students' ethical mathematics awareness as they reason through interview tasks that provoke them to make a decision based upon the results of data analytics. Drawing on multiple resources, including ethical principles from numerous STEM and business disciplines, we introduce an analytic framework for documenting the ethical mathematics awareness of adolescent students. Our findings indicate that 1) students justify their decision using a variety of ethical principles, and 2) half the students' decisions benefitted their hypothetical employer and half protected society. We conclude the paper with a discussion of implications for designing future instruction to support students' growth in ethical mathematics awareness.

Scholars in mathematics education maintain mathematics is “well integrated into the technological, industrial, military, economic and political systems of the present ‘Westernized’ world” (D’Ambrosio, 1998, p. 67). According to Lengnink (2005) the systemic influence of mathematics is a result of its embeddedness in the technology that has come to shape our world by unconsciously affecting our thinking and behavior. Unfortunately, the assumed objectivity of mathematics often generates “dehumanized thinking” which lends itself to “instrumentalism [...] ethics-free governance and social practices” (Ernest, 2018, p. 205). Benjamin (2019) appropriately labels this phenomenon *The New Jim Code*, referring to the use of technologies and, by default, mathematics to reproduce existing inequities. As such, the effects of mathematics and technology on human behavior and well-being require that mathematics become a morally and ethically grounded discipline.

Literature on the detrimental effects of mathematics on society has been expanding since the onset of globalization (D’Ignazio et al., 2020; Wheelan, 2014). O’Neil (2016) describes the discriminatory algorithms and models that have come to organize, manage, and make

Please cite as: Stephan, M., Register, J., Reinke, L., Pugalee, D., Crabtree, L., Robinson, C., & Pugalenti, P. (2021). Ethical mathematics awareness in students' big data decision making. In D. Kolloosche (Ed.), *Exploring new ways to connect: Proceedings of the Eleventh International Mathematics Education and Society Conference* (Vol. 3, pp. 977–985). Tredition. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5416678>

decisions about human lives. These mathematical models, intended to increase productivity and reduce human error, have replaced human decision-making processes in areas such as loan disbursement, insurance qualification, policing, and political campaigns. Because such algorithms are built using statistical correlations as proxies for desired information, groups who have been historically targeted for their perceived socially unacceptable behavior become trapped in a vicious cycle of self-fulfilling prophecy. In 1973, Paulo Freire warned that the influx of new technologies had the potential to develop massified consciousness, or an individual's flawed belief that humans act through free choice alone rather than by choice and manipulation. Individuals with massified consciousness participate in their own domination by uncritically accepting media reports rather than through their critical reflection on the world. To overcome such thinking, Freire (1970) introduced a pedagogy aimed at developing, critical consciousness, whereby an individual learns to "perceive social, political and economic contradictions and to take action against the oppressive elements of reality" (Freire, 1970, p. 36). Mason (1986) claims that it is the responsibility of educators to ensure that citizens possess the "intellectual skills to deal with information" including the ability to read, write, reason, and calculate (p. 10). Given the intimate role that mathematics plays in politics and policy, civic life, Information and Systems Technology, as well as the number of mathematics majors who go on to work in related industries, we argue that mathematics education should play a considerable role in preparing students for their ethical responsibilities as well.

The majority of the literature on ethics in mathematics is theoretical and/or philosophical. Few empirical studies exist which incorporate ethics into mathematics learning; the majority of these exist in the realm of Critical/Social Justice mathematics (Frankenstein, 1983; Gutstein, 2006; Kokka, 2020; Rubel, 2017). In this paper, we explore the ethical mathematics awareness of 13 middle and high school students of racial and economic privilege by analyzing their responses to tasks that involve making decisions with the results of data analytics. For this exploration, we developed an Ethical Reasoning in Mathematics (ERiM) analytic framework that is specific to data science. In this paper, we present the ERiM framework and use it to analyze adolescents' ethical mathematics reasoning.

Methodology

Our theoretical perspective is situated within the Critical Mathematics education (CM) program elaborated by Frankenstein (1983) and Shor (1993). The complementary goals of CM are to a) promote students' capacity for critical reflection so that they can question mathematical arguments, models and representations and b) inspire students' agency to act in ways that use mathematical communication to liberate, rather than disenfranchise, groups. We define the term *critical mathematics consciousness* (CMC) as a content-specific form of critical consciousness (Freire, 1970; 1973) that involves the awareness of the role that mathematics plays in disenfranchising or liberating oppressed groups in society and the willingness and commitment to act. CMC involves three different types of awareness (Stephan et al., 2021):

- *Sociopolitical Mathematics Awareness* that mathematics is used to model and interpret the real world and can be used to make decisions both at the individual and systemic levels that may be oppressive or liberatory.
- *Ethical Mathematics Awareness* that human beings do mathematics; thus there are potential ethical dilemmas and implications of mathematical work.
- *Communicative Mathematics Awareness* that mathematical communication has the power to educate and mis-educate society and encourage the masses to act in certain ways.

Like Freire, we view critical mathematics consciousness as something that can be developed with critical pedagogies.

Analytic framework

Ethical mathematics awareness refers to being aware of ethical implications that may or may not be considered in the process of making mathematical decisions, such as violations of privacy, questions of who owns the mathematical data, and bias in the data, to name a few. To create the Ethical Principles Framework in Table 1, we consulted a variety of resources including philosophy and mathematics education articles. While the general principles expressed in these resources were useful, we also suspected that more nuanced principles pertaining to the STEM professions might be found in materials published by professional organizations for engineering, data analytics, artificial intelligence, computing and information, science, and statistics. Since many of our interview questions employed a business scenario as the context for making decisions, we also explored resources from business domains including marketing, accounting, and finance.

The Ethical Principles Framework does not represent a finite list of principles, but rather a compilation of the most relevant principles for ethical reasoning in the intersection of STEM and business professions. One point of elaboration involves the distinction between fairness and discrimination. Fairness involves attempts to avoid biased decisions and thus unequal treatment towards human beings. Discrimination refers specifically to the unfairness committed upon already-oppressed groups in society.

Participants

The work presented in this article was conducted as the first step in a Design Research Project (Cobb et al., 2003) that focuses on Designing for Critical Mathematics Consciousness (CMC) among students of privilege. Interviews were conducted *primarily* with 14–16-year-old students with economic and racial privilege to a) understand their CMC and b) determine viable contextual problems that may provoke critical mathematics consciousness. The Design Research Team consists of two mathematics educators, two STEM educators, one doctoral student and one assessment professional. We interviewed thirteen students, nine of whom identified as male and four as female. Nine of the students matriculated at Hill High

Charter¹ high school, three from a Lakeview Charter middle school and one from Paradise Bluffs, a private, middle school. Thirty percent of Hill High Charter’s students perform at grade level in mathematics and the student population is 65% White, 22% Black and 5% Hispanic. Sixty-three percent of Lakeview Charter’s students perform at grade level in mathematics and the student population is 70% White, 13% Black, and 5% Hispanic. Finally, eighty percent of Paradise Bluffs’ students perform at grade level in mathematics and the student population is 75% White, 13% Black, and 1% Hispanic.

Ethical Principles	Considerations	Professional Domains Addressing the Principle
Privacy	How does respect for freedom or personal autonomy apply? Is confidentiality required? Is consent needed or obtained? Is privacy violated?	NSPE*, JMU ASA, ACM/AI
Fairness (equality)	What is the fair or just thing to do? Is there fair access to systems that are created?	ACM, AIB, Data Analytics, JMU
Accuracy	Is data reliable and accurate?	NSPE, AIB, ACM/AI, Science,
Accountability	Who is accountable? Have they communicated the data in a misleading manner? Is the source reliable?	Data Analytics
Property	Whose data is it to sell? Who owns the data?	Data Analytics
Loyalty	Is the decision/activity loyal to the organization (e.g., makes profit, keeps ideas within organization, does not use organization’s ideas to make money elsewhere)	AIB, JMU
Accessibility	What information does an organization have the right to access about people? Who has access to this data? User/buyer?	Data Analytics
Algorithm Bias	Are algorithms objective? Do algorithms (un)knowingly discriminate against individuals or groups?	AI
Transparency	Are the codes for algorithms readily available for inspection?	ACM/AI, Science, ASA
Ecological	Has the impact on humans and ecosystems been considered?	ACM/AI, NSPE
Employment	Will the decision/activity harm an individual’s or group’s employment status?	AI
Discrimination	Has the decision/activity avoided negative effects on oppressed societal groups?	Data Analytics, ACM/AI, AIB

*James Madison University Ethical Reasoning in Action (JMU); American of Statistics Association (ASA); Resnik (1998)-Science; Chessell (2014)-Data Analytics; National Society for Professional Engineers (NSPE); Association for Computing Machinery (ACM); Artificial Intelligence (AI); International Business (AIB).

Table 1. Ethical Mathematics Reasoning Framework

¹ All student and school names are pseudonyms.

Method

Interviews lasted from 25-45 minutes and took place at the student's school in a private setting during a non-academic class period such as physical education. The interviewer began each session with general talk, attempting to build rapport with the student, and then posed five tasks. Due to the brevity of the paper, we only elaborate on students' ethical awareness on the Great Groceries task below.

Great Groceries is one of the biggest successes in American grocery chains. Impressively, Great Groceries reported \$14.74 million in quarterly profits last year. You report to the CEO for Great Groceries. One of his goals for 2020 is to increase profits.

Your Management Team, based on extensive data analysis, comes up with the following three recommendations for increasing profits:

Option A: Tiered Membership Fee to shop at the store. Offer tiered membership fees, the idea being that richer customers buy more products. The Tiered-Membership Program would increase profits by 1.8%.

Option B: Raise the price on the five top selling items by \$1.50 each, increasing profits by 0.5%.

	Member's Yearly Income Level	Membership Fee per Year
Upper Tier	\$150,000 and up	free
Middle Tier	\$70,000-\$150,000	\$50
Lower Tier	\$30,000-\$70,000	\$75
Sub Tier	Under \$30,000	\$100

Option C: Put more digital, self-serve checkout stands in their stores to decrease the number of human workers, raising profits by 3.5%.

Which option would you recommend to your CEO, if any? Explain. Why didn't you suggest Option A, B, or C?

The options were designed intentionally to create a potential ethical dilemma for students between choosing an option that placed profits over people. Option A may prompt students to recognize issues of economic classism and structural oppression by imposing a shopping fee on the poorest customers. Option B, in our view, posed the least harm to people but also raised the least profit. Option C would generate the most profit but also eliminate jobs. When a student made a decision, the interviewer posed follow up questions to elicit their justifications. Each interview was transcribed and three team members used the Ethical Mathematics Reasoning Framework to categorize each student's responses independently. Once coding was completed, the three team members met to compare results and achieve consensus.

Findings

We organize the findings around two main themes. First, there were two main concerns that informed students' decisions: Consequences for a) humans and b) profits. Second, there were a variety of ethical principles invoked by students as they made their decisions.

Impact on Humans or Profit?

Of the thirteen students who answered the Great Groceries question, six picked the option that they considered to have the least harmful impact on humans. Two students indicated that they would choose option C because they felt their personal employment status depended upon recommending the option that would bring in the largest profit; these students indicated that if they did not have to report to the CEO, they would choose the least harmful option. The remaining five students chose the option they perceived to be best for the business, in terms of increase in profits.

Jamal's reasoning is one example of instances where students anticipated how their decision might negatively impact humans.

Jamal: I pick option B [be]cause like, um, option C taking people's jobs didn't sound right and because people need money too, to help their families. And option A, just helping the richer customers is, it's not really cool.

For Jamal, Option B offered the best possible outcome for people "because it doesn't seem like it's doing anything bad..." However, Option A was not fair because some people, most notably the rich, were getting something for free while others had to "pay a fine."

While five students eliminated Option C, seven other students articulated their loyalty to the company by choosing it. For example, Collin recognized the impact that choosing Option C would have on humans, yet made his decision based upon what yielded the highest profit.

Collin: It's kind of hard because you're also putting so many people [out of] the jobs. But that would also mean you wouldn't have to pay them. You wouldn't have to pay them at all. So yes, your profit would go up. So I guess, C.

Int: All right, how come you didn't do option B?

Collin: Because if the top five selling goods are already selling at their price and you bump it up a dollar 50 maybe those people won't want to buy it anymore.

For Collin, his commitment was to increase profit for the company, despite recognizing the negative impact on employment of the workers. He continued to rationalize his decision by arguing that minimizing the number of workers would decrease salary expenses, raising profits even more. Even when asked if he did not have a CEO to report to, Collin still chose Option C.

Jade, on the other hand, changed her decision when given the opportunity not to report to the CEO. Her initial decision was Option C, possibly due to her belief that her primary loyalty was to her employer even though it conflicted with her ethical beliefs.

Jade: I think the last option probably would be the best just based on how this one is 1.8% this is 0.5 and this is 3.5 but at the same time...although this raises profits it does put a lot of people out of jobs, which also isn't a good thing for the rest of everyone...Um, I don't think that's [Option B] a bad one, but it doesn't have the best increase of profit. And at the same time it does make things more expensive. So you might lose customers.

Ethical mathematics awareness in students' big data decision making

Jade: [Interviewer gives her the choice not to report to the CEO] Oh yeah, I would probably say the first one then because, um, well you're not forcing everyone to pay an extra dollar 50 and, if you can afford the membership, then you'll get the membership...You don't have to worry about like the moral part of it. Um employment, making sure people get paid and can support themselves.

In the exchanges above, Jade recognized the impact that choosing Option C has on the livelihood of humans due to losing their means of supporting themselves. However, her loyalty to the CEO and the company compelled her to make an "amoral" decision. Although she did not recognize the negative impact of Option A on families that live in poverty, she nevertheless, chose what, to her, was the least hurtful option when the possibility of not reporting to the CEO was posed.

In summary, about half of the students we interviewed made their decision by considering the impact that it would make on human beings, while roughly half remained loyal to the company. Two of those seven however, changed to a less harmful Option when relieved of the criterion to report to the CEO. As we will see in the next section, students evoked several ethical principles as they decided which option to recommend.

Other ethical principles

In the previous section, we documented the end result of students' reasoning on Great Groceries and learned that the number of students making choices based primarily upon negative consequences for humans was about equal to the number who considered the positive effects on the company's profits. There were six ethical principles evoked by students as they justified their decision: Employment, Fairness, Loyalty, Accuracy, Discrimination, and Privacy.

Eight of the thirteen students mentioned the impact that their decision would have on *employment*. Five of those eight argued that choosing Option C would negatively affect people whose means of supporting themselves would be compromised. Another student, Miya, did not choose Option C, but her reference to employment actually focused on the negative impact that unemployment has on the economy, not the family. Finally, two students who chose Option C commented on employment arguing either that people would lose jobs but profits would go up (Collin above) or did not acknowledge the impact on workers at all, just increase in profit.

Six students mentioned *fairness* in their justifications saying that it was not fair that some people had to pay more than others just to get in the store. Some of the students' arguments indicated that they noticed it was the poor who were being made to pay more than the rich and exhibited empathy for the unfairness. Only one student made connections to systemic discrimination in this Option which we identify as the Discrimination principle.

Of the six students who used *loyalty* to justify their decision, not surprisingly, all of them chose the Option that they perceived would generate the highest profit.

Four students questioned the *accuracy* of the profit predictions made in some of the options. Accuracy refers to questioning the data both in terms of reliability and validity.

Although the students did not refer to the data that was used to create these options, they did question the viability of the options, or as Miya said: “I don’t like Option A. It just doesn’t, they’re just *thinking*. They don’t have the math for it. They can’t just say that.” In other words, Miya suggested that the Option creators were merely conjecturing (thinking) rather than using data (math). In terms of *privacy*, only one student mentioned this principle in regards to Option A. Ella argued that she would choose Option A, over Option C, only if the customers’ plans could be kept private so that they were not aware of the higher fee they may be paying (implying a fairness issue).

Only one student made his decision (Option B) based upon recognizing what he perceived to be *discriminatory* practices in two of the options.

Tyrone: Definitely not option A...So if even if the idea worked out, you’re cheating out the lower class who only received \$30,000, and they have to pay a membership fee of \$100...that’s a lot of money and no one would really spend that much money that’s in poverty on their tier with \$100. And it’s kinda like taxes, wealthier, I know a lot of popular companies don’t have to spend money on taxes, but they’re the ones who have the most. Option B [is] the most fair route I would go because everything else is just like morally incorrect. That’s mean, morally incorrect because you’re taxing, um, poverty. And then option C...I don’t want to decrease jobs because people still need jobs. And, um, I know a lot of the grocery store occupation is like located with people in poverty, high-schoolers and retirement, people in retirement. So I don’t think it’s fair to any of those groups because they’re the ones most troubled...

We categorized Tyrone’s reasoning as recognizing the discrimination that could occur as the result of carrying out Options A and C. Tyrone attended to the oppression that would be inflicted (fees; taxes) on already oppressed groups of people (people in poverty) by systems (wealthy companies; governments). Not only did he foresee the negative impact of his decision in the Great Groceries Dilemma but also recognized systemic injustices that are sometimes perpetuated by the taxation system in his country.

In summary, the students employed a variety of ethical principles as they deliberated the impact of their business decisions. Students almost evenly split on staying loyal to the company by increasing profits or making decisions that would not impact the livelihood of citizens negatively. Attending to the employment of citizens was the top ethical principle evoked by students. It should be noted that two students questioned the ethics of Option B by considering which particular items are best sellers. For example, Miya and Greta thought it would be unethical to raise the prices on what were likely top sellers at the time of the interview (the COVID-19 pandemic), toilet paper and hand sanitizer.

Conclusion

Our analysis indicated that middle and high school students have indeed developed quite a repertoire of ethical principles and employ them as they consider situations that potentially call for empathy and subsequent action. At least half of the students chose options that they

perceived would have the least negative consequences for humans with one student noticing potential systemic discrimination. The students who exhibited loyalty to the company and its profits either did not notice the negative potential outcomes of the other choices or felt obligated to choose profits as a part of their job. Or as Tony put it, “when you’re running a business, it’s about profit.” We see problems such as Great Groceries as rich contexts for discussions about the accuracy of the data-driven options, issues of fairness and discrimination and whether profits or the safety and livelihood of citizens should drive data-based decision making.

References

- Benjamin, R. (2019). *Race after technology: Abolitionist tools for the new Jim Code*. Polity Press.
- Chessell, M. (2014). *Ethics for big data and analytics*. Retrieved on January 8, 2021, from <https://www.ibmbigdatahub.com/whitepaper/ethics-big-data-and-analytics>
- Cobb, P., Confrey, J., diSessa, A., Lehrer, R., & Schauble, L. (2003). Design experiments in education research. *Educational Researcher*, 32(1), 9–13.
- D’Ambrosio, U. (1998) Mathematics and peace: Our responsibilities. *Zentralblatt für Didaktik der Mathematik*, 30(3), 67–73. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02653170>
- D’Ignazio, C., & Klein, L. F. (2020). *Data feminism*. The MIT Press.
- Ernest, P. (2018). The ethics of mathematics: Is mathematics harmful? In P. Ernest (Ed.), *The philosophy of mathematics education today* (pp. 187–216). Springer.
- Frankenstein, M. (1983). Critical mathematics education: An application of Paulo Freire’s epistemology. *Journal of Education*, 165(4), 315–339.
- Freire, P. (1970). *Pedagogy of the oppressed*. Continuum.
- Freire, P. (1973). *Education for critical consciousness*. Press.
- Gutstein, E. (2006). *Reading and writing the world with mathematics: Toward a pedagogy for social justice*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203112946>
- Lengnink, K. (2005) Reflecting mathematics: An approach to achieve mathematical literacy. *Zentralblatt für Didaktik der Mathematik*, 37(3), 246–249.
- Kokka, K. (2020). Social justice pedagogy for whom? Developing privileged students’ critical mathematics consciousness. *The Urban Review*, 52, 778–803. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11256-020-00578-8>
- Mason, R. (1986). Ethical issues of the information age. *MIS Quarterly*, 10(1), 5–12.
- O’Neil, C. (2016). *Weapons of math destruction: How big data increases inequality and threatens democracy*. Crown.
- Resnik, D. (1998). *The ethics of science: An introduction*. Routledge.
- Rubel, L. (2017). Equity-directed instructional practices: Beyond the dominant perspective. *Journal of Urban Mathematics Education*, 10(2), 66–105.
- Shor, I. (1993). Education is politics: Paulo Freire’s critical pedagogy. In P. Leonard & P. McLaren (Eds.), *Paulo Freire: A critical encounter* (p. 25–35). Routledge.
- Stephan, M., Register, J., Reinke, L., Robinson, C., Pugalenti, P., & Pugalee, D. (2021). People use math as a weapon: Critical mathematics consciousness in the time of COVID-19. *Educational Studies in Mathematics*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10649-021-10062-z>
- Wheelan, C. J. (2014). *Naked statistics stripping the dread from the data*. Norton.